

Information in Contemplative Practice: The Generation of Novel Insight

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Focus whether sustained or transient generates novel information. The arising of this kind of information likely involves the interfacing of existent knowledge that is embedded within systems. For instance, in different contemplative practices, one works with disturbing feelings or emotions with the aim of ameliorating them. This can be a wellspring of new information but only if the intention is to inhabit a state of watchful abiding and not knowledge. Knowledge in this context means anything that describes and perpetuates our usual way of being, that of responses to fix, change or replace the causes of our distress. That is perhaps the most innate property of systems, one that abrogates the arising of new information, that of resistance to flux and decay. Focus is essentially a state of minimal definition, open to possibility.

Our perception of difficult feelings and thoughts can be the source of new information but only if we try and avoid our usual response of replacing one system of knowledge with another. Not only does this mean freedom from dependence on knowledge, it heralds a state of 'no measure'. It might be safe to say that all systems including us abide within a continuum of measure, and this state of measure tends to approach what this author describes as 'no measure'. System knowledge is a state of measure and while conventional observation seems to reveal dynamicity, in terms of 'no measure', it is static. It is only the system-wide tendency to approach no measure that lends a certain degree of true movement.

Resistance to this tendency to approach a state of 'no measure' generates perturbation and is likely an innate characteristic common to all systems. This gravity as it were, is not uniformly distributed and in conjunction with the tendency to approach 'no measure' gives rise to discrete quanta of information that exist in a graded spectrum of being. What this really means is that a state that exists with the maximum possible degree of freedom is converted by measure and resistance as described above into matter that is again and then repeatedly, variably measured!

What does all this mean in terms of contemplative practice? It means that any state of definition is limiting. This definition upon measure gives rise to either joy or distress which are, though not equally, forms of entrapment. Not knowing has been described by some contemplative traditions as conducive to a considerable degree of freedom and when consistently practiced allows the generation of new information that is free of the knowledge brought about by systems interfacing. Thus, the state of not knowing affords a simple peace in silence that doesn't seek any particular definition. This state of minimal measure when consistently engaged in can yield new information and novel insights.

REFERENCES:

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